

Youths’s Emotional Intelligence at Softenmind Psychological Support Company, Ho Chi Minh City

Le Thi Hang

Master's student in Psychology, University of Science and Education, University of Danang

ARTICLE INFO	ABSTRACT
<p>Published Online: 17 May 2024</p> <p>Corresponding Author: Le Thi Hang</p>	<p>Emotional intelligence is the intelligence that demonstrates a correct understanding of emotions and the ability to handle one's own emotions and to empathize and share with others. Emotional intelligence is significant in the development process of young people, because they are an important human resource for the country in the future. Research results on the level and expression of emotional intelligence of young people at Softenmind company, Ho Chi Minh City using the emotional intelligence scale of D.V. Lyusin. Research results show that 43.1% of young people have a very low level of emotional intelligence, only 3.9% have a very high level. From the above results, the study proposes a number of measures to improve Emotional intelligence for young people at Softenmind company.</p>
<p>KEYWORDS: intelligence, emotional intelligence, emotional intelligence of young people</p>	

1. ASK THE PROBLEM

Emotional intelligence is the intelligence that demonstrates a correct understanding of emotions and the ability to handle one's own emotions and to empathize and share with others. Emotional intelligence is formed in the early years of life and continues to develop until adulthood. For young people, learning to understand and develop emotional abilities is very important. This helps young people improve their emotional abilities and create a foundation for the development of emotional intelligence. Good emotional preparation at this stage will help young people be confident and brave in their future careers.

According to David Wechsler (1943), one of the first people to introduce IQ testing, recognized the importance of emotional factors. He has mentioned emotional intelligence and social intelligence in his articles.

Next, R. Bar - On (1997) considered emotional intelligence within the scope of personality theory, introducing the Well - being model, in which personality characteristics are said to determine success in life. In addition to cognitive intelligence, there are five areas with fifteen factors. He proposed the Emotional Quotient Inventory - (EQ - i), he approached emotional intelligence in a mixed model using self-reported scales to assess emotional intelligence. EQ - i measures a range of noncognitive skills, potentials, and abilities that influence a person's ability to succeed in coping with environmental pressures and demands.

IQ often fails to explain differences in the fortunes of individuals who initially appear similar. When looking back at life, those who achieved the best results in exams were not as successful as others in terms of salary and career position. Furthermore, they are no happier in their private lives. Therefore, each person needs to improve their emotional intelligence, especially youth, which is an important stage in life to have a truly happy life.

To assess the current status of emotional intelligence of young people, thereby proposing programs to improve the emotional intelligence of young people, forming the necessary skills and abilities to develop the personalities of young people and students. Together with softenmind Company, we conducted an assessment of this situation on 65 young people in Ho Chi Minh City (HCMC).

2. THEORETICAL BASIS

P. Salovey and J. Mayer (1990) introduced the concept of emotional intelligence: "Emotional intelligence is the ability to understand one's own emotions, understand the emotions of others, distinguish them and use them." that information to guide your thinking and actions." In 1997, P. Salovey and J. Mayer limited emotional intelligence to the concept of intellectual ability and separated it from emotional personality traits. Traditional social contact, this model is called the EI 97 model, this model is recognized and stable to date. Emotional intelligence is defined: "Emotional

intelligence refers to the ability to perceive the meanings of emotions and the relationships between them, to reason and solve problems on the basis of these meanings and relationships. that relationship. Emotional intelligence is involved in the abilities to perceive emotions, assimilate feelings related to emotions, understand information about those emotions and manage them.”

Boyatzis scale (1999) – Emotion scale designed for self-assessment and other-assessment. This scale is designed based on the definition of emotional intelligence as the ability to recognize one's own emotions and those of others to motivate oneself, manage, control one's emotions and control management. relationships with others.

The ECI test measures 4 areas of emotional intelligence: 1/. Self-awareness: recognize your emotions, evaluate yourself accurately, be confident; 2/. Self-control, self-mastery, self-control of emotions, self-confidence, self-awareness, adaptability, achievement orientation and creativity; 3/. Recognize social relationships: empathize, know how to organize and orient service; 4/. Social skills: educating others, leadership capacity, influencing capacity, communication capacity, catalyzing change, control, conflict management, building relationships, spirit spirit of teamwork and cooperation. The above competencies are measured by asking the information provider to evaluate and asking the subject himself/herself to evaluate himself/herself through a self-assessment multiple choice version.

Cooper's EQ Map (1996, 1997) This measurement divides emotional intelligence into five components: 1/. Current environment: measures life pressures and personal satisfaction; 2/. Emotional understanding: measures the ability to recognize one's own emotions, express emotions and recognize the emotions of others; 3/. Emotional intelligence competencies: measure the ability to use emotions purposefully, be creative, be flexible, relate to others, and resolve dissatisfaction positively; 4/. Values and attitudes: including vision, love, intuition, trust, personal power and self-integration; 5/. Outcomes: measures the visible outcomes of emotional intelligence, including general health, quality of life, relationship metrics, and optimal work performance.

According to Daniel Goleman (2011), the causes of emotional intelligence are innate, acquired during life, self-trained, guided, trained, etc.

From the above bases, the writer proposes a questionnaire to investigate the manifestations of emotional intelligence and its effects. The effects of emotional intelligence limit harshness or aggression, improving the ability to understand and control emotions. Helps people make better decisions about life's problems and have optimism. Enhance determination and team spirit. Improve cooperation skills and help each other in studying and training. Helps people understand themselves and others.

3. OBJECTS AND RESEARCH METHODS

3.1. Object

Survey conducted on 65 young people at the psychological support company Softenmind, Ho Chi Minh City

3.2. Method

- Questionnaire survey method: we built a questionnaire consisting of 4 parts, perceptions of emotional intelligence, effects of emotional intelligence on life, causes of formation, and effective measures. can enhance emotional intelligence.

- In-depth interview method: We interviewed some young people about their awareness of emotional intelligence to clarify the content of the study.

- Multiple choice method.

We use the emotional intelligence scale of D.V. Lyusin to measure the ability to understand and control the emotions of yourself and others. Target users: from 16-67 years old. The content of the scale includes 46 questions, corresponding to the values of the following scales:

- MEI scale (Interpersonal EQ): Ability to understand other people's emotions and control them.

- VEI scale (Intrapersonality EQ): Ability to understand personal emotions and control them.

- PE scale (understanding emotions): The ability to understand the emotions of yourself and others.

- UE Scale (Emotional Control): The ability to control one's own and other people's emotions.

- MP subscale (understanding other people's emotions): The ability to understand other people's emotional states on the basis of external emotional expressions (face, gestures and voice) and/or intuition. have a cold; sensitive to the internal state of others.

- MU subscale (controlling other people's emotions): Ability to evoke emotions in others, reduce unnecessary emotions and have the ability to control others.

- VP subscale (understanding one's own emotions): The ability to understand one's own emotional states: Can recognize and identify them, understand the causes of emotions and the ability to describe them with words. word.

- VU subscale (controlling one's own emotions): The ability and need to control one's own emotions, evoke and maintain necessary emotions, and control unnecessary emotions.

- VE subscale (expressive control): The ability to control external expressions of one's emotions.

How to conduct the test:

Before conducting the test, the tester introduces the purpose, requirements and meaning of the test to the tester. Then, proceed with these steps:

Step 1: Give each candidate a test set and an answer sheet and instructions

Instructions to write all information on the answer sheet.

Step 2: Instructions for taking the test.

Step 3: You can conduct a test.

Step 4: Collect the test sheet when the test is completed.

Emotional intelligence is calculated as follows:

$$MEI = MP + MU$$

$$VEI = VP + VU + VE$$

$$PE = MP + VP$$

$$UE = MU + VU + VE$$

$$EI \text{ (sum of EQ scales)} = MP + MU + VP + VU + VE$$

Mathematical statistical method: We use SPSS 26.6 software to analyze average score data; ratio %; Standard deviation, comparative correlation in intelligence groups.

4. RESEARCH RESULTS

4.1. Awareness of emotional intelligence

The survey results in table 1 show that 88.7% of young people at Softenmind company, Ho Chi Minh City chose the option of emotional intelligence as the ability to recognize their own and other people's emotions; Self-motivation and ability to manage emotions well within oneself and in relationships with others. This is also the correct answer for the emotional intelligence awareness section. Meanwhile, 8.1% of young people think that emotional intelligence is the ability to recognize one's own and other people's emotions and 3.2% of young people think that the ability to perceive other people's emotions and promote emotional management is important. Contact in relationships.

Table 1. Ability to recognize emotional intelligence Content Ratio

The ability to recognize one's own emotions and those of others.	8.1%
The capacity to perceive the emotions of others and promote emotional management in relationships.	3.2%
The ability to recognize one's own emotions and those of others; Self-motivation and ability to manage emotions well within oneself and in relationships with others.	88.7 %

From the above numbers, it shows that the level of awareness of emotional intelligence of young people is very high, but besides that, there are also cases of incorrect awareness and awareness but not necessarily understanding and actually being successful in using it. emotional intelligence, which shows that improving emotional intelligence for young people is very important, because this is an audience with in-depth knowledge that can create innovations in their lives and create future development of society.

Through the data obtained in chart 1, 51.6% of young people are aware that the role of emotional intelligence in human success in general and in learning in particular is very important, and 34.4% is important, only 7.8% think it is not important at all, 1.6% choose not important, and 4.7% think it is okay or not, opinions show that the number The number of young people who are highly aware of the role of emotional intelligence in success is not small, so improving emotional intelligence is important.

Figure 1: Recognizing the role of emotional intelligence

Research on the assessment of the level of emotional intelligence of young people, from table 2 of the results of the study of the level of assessment of emotional intelligence factors for 65 young people, the highest result is the perception of emotional intelligence factors for 65 young people. Knowing one's own emotions with a score of 3.23,

while the lowest level is the ability to control the emotions of others with only 2.41. From the above data, it shows that the number of young people aware of the levels of emotional intelligence is above a moderate level, partly due to a lack of understanding of emotional intelligence.

Table 2: Perceived level of emotional intelligence levels of young people

Nội dung	Are not	get little	okay	Good	Medium score	standard deviation	Order
1. You recognize your emotions	1,6%	6,3%	59,4%	32,8%	3,23	,636	1
2. You recognize other people's emotions when you interact	1,6%	25,4%	49,2%	3,8%	2,95	,750	5
3. You understand and analyze your own emotions	3,1%	10,9%	57,8%	28,1%	3,11	,715	2
4. You understand and analyze other people's emotions	6,6%	26,2%	54,1%	13,1%	2,74	,772	9
5. You use emotions in work and communication	3,1%	14,1%	53,1%	29,7%	3,09	,750	3
6. You manage your emotions	4,8%	20,6%	52,4%	22,2%	2,92	,789	7
7. You control other people's emotions	20,6%	28,6%	39,7%	11,1%	2,41	,944	10
8. You have empathy	0%	17,5%	60,3%	22,2%	3,05	,633	4
9. You have social skills	4,8%	27,0%	52,4%	15,9%	2,79	,765	8
10. You are motivated to take action.	4,8%	15,9%	60,3%	19,0%	2,94	,738	6

4.2. The level of expression of emotional intelligence

4.2.1 Expression level of emotional intelligence

Through the results of table 3 of the survey on young people at the psychological support company Softenmind, it shows that very low emotional intelligence accounts for the most number with 43.1%, while very high intelligence accounts for only 3.9%. Besides the low levels of 9.8%, and

high levels of 11.8%, the majority of emotional intelligence is at an average level, with a rate of 31.4%, this shows emotional intelligence capacity. of young people is only average and very low, we pose the problem that there is a need for specific guidance to improve emotional intelligence for young people.

Table 3: Emotional intelligence results of young people at Softenmind company

Intellectual group	Rất thấp	Short	Medium	High	Very high
EI overall emotional intelligence index (EQ)	43,1%	9,8%	31,4%	11,8%	3,9%

4.2.2 Level of expression of emotional intelligence manifestations

Analyzing the general results of emotional intelligence of young people at Softenmind company, Ho Chi Minh City, presented in table 4, we see:

MEI (Interpersonal EQ) expression aspect: The ability to understand other people's emotions and control them of young people in Ho Chi Minh City with 30.5% at a very low level, the highest compared to the number of survey participants. , 23.7% is low, 23.7% is medium and high is 16.9%, very high index is only 5.1%. The difference between

the highest and lowest levels is very high, which shows that the ability to understand and control the emotions of others needs to be improved. The emotional intelligence side is mainly directed outward, towards others. This component requires young people to be able to control their own emotions expressed in relationships with others, in work, and in cooperation. For young people, who live in a less-changing environment and are constantly protected by school and family, personal relationships are based on knowing and understanding each other. Therefore, they have less contact with complex social situations and less life experience.

Therefore, when they encounter strange and complicated situations, they are easily confused and do not handle them effectively.

VEI expression side (Intrapersonality EQ): The ability of young people to understand their own emotions and control them is not much different from the Interpersonal expression side, from the data it shows that there are up to 32, 1% of the emotional intelligence index at a very low level is almost equal to the very low level of (interpersonal EQ), and the indexes at the low level of 28.6%, the average of 32.1% also account for a large number. , while the high index is 3.6% and the very high index is only 3.6%, this is remarkable, when realizing through the survey results that both the ability to understand and control emotions are low. The intellectual component of self-experience of emotions is mainly directed at the self, including aspects of recognizing the emotions that are happening in the self. Meanwhile, young people's relationships mainly take place within the framework of school and family, notably friendship relationships that take place during learning activities. The environment makes young people have similarities in their emotional, emotional and cognitive lives.

It is difficult for children to have self-control, control their own emotions and calm themselves down to escape negative emotions. Therefore, the level of interpersonal expression reaches a lower level than the level of intrapersonality. Interviewing student T.T.L, class 17, we learned: "There are times when I feel empty, I don't know if I'm sad or happy, I can't describe it in words, sometimes I have many mixed emotions that I don't know. I can't name it, and it's very difficult to control my emotions when I'm sad or angry."

PE expression (understanding emotions): The ability to understand emotions of yourself and others through data shows that 51.8% of the index is very low, 19.6% low, 25.0% average average and 3.6% are high, while the very high index is 0%, which means no one can achieve this level. Among the abilities, understanding one's emotions is the most important thing, but comparing the number of 65 young people, no one reached a very high level as well as a very few high level compared to a very low level, shows that young people in the age of virtual technology do not clearly know

what their real emotions are. Through an in-depth interview with H.V.D, 19 years old, she said: "Sometimes I don't clearly understand why I like or dislike some people, and there are angry situations that I can't immediately see." when I start to get angry."

UE expression aspect (Emotional control): The ability to control one's own emotions and those of others, young people measured by multiple choice tests as well as in-depth interviews all have similar comments. Through an in-depth interview with 25-year-old N.M.C. After working for 3 years in the company, he shared: "In difficult situations, I cannot force my will to push myself. I feel dissatisfied when If I don't do something well, it's very difficult for me to change my emotions to make life more positive. It's hard for me to help those who are sharing their feelings with me."

Faces of MP expression. The ability to understand the emotional state of others on the basis of external emotional expressions (facial, gestures and voice) and/or premonitions; Sensitive to the internal state of others with 43.3% of young people only reaching a very low level, accounting for a lot of the survey. MU (controlling the emotions of others): Ability to evoke emotions in others, reduce unnecessary emotions and have the ability to control others of young people with a very low 6.5%, 33, 9% low, 37.1% average, 14.5% high and 8.1% very high, it can be seen that the level of controlling other people's emotions is not high.

For aspects of VP expression (understanding one's own emotions): The ability to understand one's own emotional states, to be able to recognize and identify them, to understand the causes of emotions and the ability to describe emotions. describe in words, VU controls one's emotions): The ability and need to control one's emotions, evoke and maintain necessary emotions, control unnecessary emotions, VE (expressive control): The ability to control the external expressions of one's own emotions through a survey of expression levels that are neither too high nor too low, usually at an average level.

As can be observed in Table 4, we make objective comments about the low level of expression of young people's emotional intelligence, requiring a support program to improve emotional intelligence in the future. .

Table 4: Emotional intelligence level of young people at Softenmind company

Intellectual group	Very low	Short	Medium	High	Very high
MP The ability to understand the emotional state of others on the basis of external emotional expressions (facial, gestures and voice) and/or premonitions; sensitive to the internal state of others	43,3%	18,3%	21,7%	11,7%	5,0%
MU (manipulating the emotions of others): The ability to evoke emotions in others, reduce unnecessary emotions and have the ability to control others	6,5%	33,9%	37,1%	14,5%	8,1%

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VP (understanding one's own emotions): The ability to understand one's own emotional states: Being able to recognize and identify them, understanding the causes of emotions and the ability to describe them in words.	8,5%	37,3%	44,1%	10,2%	0%
VU Controlling one's own emotions): The ability and need to control one's own emotions, evoke and maintain necessary emotions, and control unnecessary emotions	11,7%	36,7%	30,0%	13,3%	8,3%
VE (expressive control): The ability to control the external expressions of one's emotions	17,2%	51,6%	26,6%	4,7%	0%
MEI (Interpersonal EQ): The ability to understand other people's emotions and control them	30,5%	23,7%	23,7%	16,9%	5,1%
VEI Intrapersonality EQ): The ability to understand one's emotions and control them	32,1%	28,6%	32,1%	3,6%	3,6%
PE (emotional understanding): The ability to understand one's own and other people's emotions	51,8%	19,6%	25,0%	3,6%	0%
UE (Emotional control): The ability to control one's own emotions and those of others	3,4%	44,8%	20,7%	22,4%	8,6%
EI overall emotional intelligence quotient (EQ)	43,1%	9,8%	31,4%	11,8%	3,9%

4.2.3. Results of research on measures to improve emotional intelligence

From the results of Table 5, it shows that the objects for improving emotional intelligence are very necessary for

life, through training emotional intelligence is essential with a score above 3.1 compared to a scale of 4. This is proof that the research subjects were eager to improve their emotional intelligence.

Table 5: Measures to improve emotional intelligence for young people at Softenmind company

Content	Unnecessary	Little needed	Necessary	Very necessary	Medium score	standard deviation	Order
1. Actively and actively learn about emotional intelligence.	1.6%	3.1%	56.3%	39.1%	3.33	.619	2
2. Schools need to increase talks and training sessions to improve emotional intelligence for young people.	1.6%	16.1%	53.2%	29.0%	3.10	.718	5
3. Actively search for textbooks and reference materials on emotional intelligence.	1.6%	15.6%	51.6%	31.3%	3.13	.724	4
4. Teachers teach extremely well equipped emotional intelligence knowledge to students.	3.1%	4.7%	59.4%	32.8%	3.22	.678	3
5. Parents promote the development of children's emotional intelligence in home education.	0%	1.6%	39.5%	59.4%	3.58	.529	1

Subjective and objective factors also have a significant impact on emotional intelligence. It can be seen

that young people need to have the right and appropriate method of training emotional intelligence to train their

emotional intelligence. self, learn more about emotional intelligence, etc. Interviewing 19-year-old N.H.D, she said: "Because I am not fully aware of the role of emotional intelligence, I have no method to train my intelligence." Emotional intelligence is correct and suitable for yourself. I think it is necessary to learn and practice the methods persistently to get good results. I think we should practice mindfulness to understand and control emotions better."

5. CONCLUSION

From the above practical research results, we have obtained some conclusions:

The current state of emotional intelligence of young people at Softenmind Company in Ho Chi Minh City with a high level of emotional intelligence awareness of 88.7%.

But through survey data using the emotional intelligence scale of D.V. Lyusin on the manifestation aspects of emotional intelligence, found that the level of understanding emotional intelligence of young people is low and very low, with 51.8% being very low in the aspect of understanding one's own emotions, total The EQ index of 43.1% of young people is also at a very low level. Factors affecting emotional intelligence are also rated quite highly with an average score of over 3.8 on a 5-point scale, and assessments of the impact of emotional intelligence on all aspects of life are also high. Quite high, with 45.3% affecting Stress levels and 50.8% affecting anxiety. When considering the causes of emotional intelligence, 54.0% of young people think that self-training has a great influence on the formation of emotional intelligence. When evaluated about measures to improve emotional intelligence, most young people agree and think that improving emotional intelligence is very necessary. Thereby showing that life factors affect emotional intelligence and emotional intelligence itself also greatly affects the lives of young people in Ho Chi Minh City, especially young people in Ho Chi Minh City. Softenmind Company.

From there, research to carry out programs to improve emotional intelligence in order to form the skills and abilities necessary to develop young people's personalities and improve the mental health of young people in general is essential. And at Softenmind company in the near future.

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